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The Politics of Vitality: Plead for Animism and Protection of Nature in Select Writings of Amitav Ghosh

Mrityunjoy Samanta,
Assistant Professor,
Department of English,
Maharaja Nandakumar Mahavidyalaya,
Purba Medinipur, West Bengal, India.

Abstract: *Mankind has wrought havoc on ecological poise in this planet and his avaricious soul has fizzled out to hearken to her voice. Being quite negligent of the perils embedded in his actions, he has rendered nature quite dead. The clear division between nature and culture in modern times has outlived its moral and epistemological efficiency. The so-called sustainable period of Holocene has yielded passage to the dreaded archaeological era called the Anthropocene. So to sustain life upon this planet a radical re-examination of the relation between the human and the non-humans has been the need of the hour. In a broader sense, two distinct thoughts are there to usher sustainability of nature- the Westernized view of preservation and the indigenous view of protection of nature. The latter concept adheres much to the animistic view of the world of nature- a view shared by many of the primitive indigenous people across the globe. Animism is the belief that plants, objects, weather and other natural objects have a living soul and that there is a power that controls and organizes the universe. Like human rights, animism pleads for ecological rights and animal rights. Some writers like Amitava Ghosh, Mamang Dai and some others in the North East of India, writers on Maori tribes in New Zealand have expressed their strong faith in animism for the sustainability of nature. As part of my research in this paper, I am keen on focusing on the literary representation of animistic faith in some of the texts of Amitava Ghosh (*The Living Mountain, Gun Island, and The Hungry Tide*), and thereby*

promote across the globe, what Ghosh says, the 'politics of vitality' for the protection of nature- a belief that all living beings have a vital force.

Keywords: animism, politics of vitality, primitivism, ecology, sustainability.

The geological era called the Holocene, believed to have started 11700 years back since after the last glacial period, is the most stable part in Earth's history that finds the growth of a rich biodiversity in this planet. The worst part of Holocene, called the Anthropocene, presumably starting in the 1950s, has witnessed the steady decline in the equilibrium of that rich bio-diversity of nature. Mankind alone has wrought havoc on the sanity of nature for his aggression for development, growth of GDP, and a countless other factors, all contributing to the loss of sustainability of our habitat. The emission of greenhouse gases causing global warming, burning of forests and fossil fuels, reckless mining, nuclear explosion, chemical waste, all substantially add up to the ruin of bio-sphere of this planet. There is no denying that humankind has identified the potential threats looming large across the globe. Over the recent years, there is an increasing discussion on climate change and the loss of planetary bio-diversity. Critics, scholars, academicians, social scientists, environmentalists, so to say, the environmental humanists, are all trying different means to cope up with that challenge. On private and political levels, sincere efforts are being triggered to create an inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable environment. There have emerged multiple discourses across multiple disciplines, myriad experiments in different territories of the world, with the view to carving out new perspectives on environmental humanities. In his article *Anthropocene Time* (2018), Dipesh Chakrabarty underscores how "humankind . . . rivals some of the great forces of Nature in its impact on the functioning of the Earth system,"(6) and has become "a global geological force in its own right" (6).

To cope up with the environmental challenges there is no one "single rational solution" (Chakrabarty, "Postcolonial Studies"13).

This is exactly what Chakrabarty maintains in *Postcolonial Studies and the Challenge of Climate Change* (2012): “Precisely because there is no single rational solution, there is the need to struggle to make our way in hitherto uncharted ways”. His arguments are indicative of certain comprehensive interdisciplinary studies across “ontological and non-ontological modes of existence” (14). Donna J. Haraway in her enunciation of the “Chthulucene” (2016) sees the possibility of a revived tie between human and more-than-human entities. In *Defiant Earth: The Fate of Humans in the Anthropocene* (2017), Clive Hamilton perceives a kindred potential, optimistically earmarking humans as a ‘conscious force’: “the future of the entire planet, including many forms of life, is now contingent on the decisions of a conscious force” (27). All these, therefore, necessitate a re-situating of Hamilton’s “conscious force” or Chakrabarty “struggle” for “hitherto uncharted ways” in “a dynamic, discipline-crossing field that combines academic scholarship with environmental activism”(Hubbell and Ryan 127). J. Andrew Hubbell and John C. Ryan refer to this as “EH” in Introduction to the *Environmental Humanities* (2022). To battle against the challenges posed by environment and bio-diversity of Earth, many means of conscious forces have been suggested by the environmental humanists. Two basic kinds of conscious forces for sustainability have been suggested so far- the Westernised view of Preservation and the indigenous way of Protection. One such “conscious force” of Protection of nature reminds us of what Amitav Ghosh says, “the politics of vitality”. Such a belief has its root in the indigenous cultural belief in animism. In fact, Ghosh's "politics of vitality" is anticipation for taking a new leap to see how humans interact with the non-human world, making a shift from colonial mode of seeing nature as inert resources to recognition of nature's inherent agency and life force. He pleads for drawing on indigenous wisdom to foster harmony, co-existence, and a shared planetary fate, particularly relevant against the backdrop of climate crisis. He also warns against its co-option in the praxis of narrow nationalism or fascism. It is a belief that is based on the interconnectedness of human struggles with ecological collapse, demanding solidarity with marginalized

peoples and non-human voices. Of course, such a view was not unknown to mankind; it was not “unchartered” in the true sense. It existed but not popularised owing to the impact of other majoritarian principles of religions. In this research article I have tried to explore how some of the writers of our contemporary times, have resorted to the representation and revival of that same spirit of animism against the backdrop of echo-disaster. Some of the environmentalists and philosophers in our times have resorted to reclaim the pristine, primitive cultural narrative of animism for an understanding of the environment that necessitates conservation, management of its resources, and sustainability. In this regard, a shift towards animism is to find an alternative means of heralding a consciousness in the global arena for conservation and sustainability. Val Plumwood, in this connection is very particular in her opinion. According to her, the revival of interest for non-human phenomena is part of our survival strategy. She puts forward the argument that it is emergent in our times to rethink and hair-split the cultural narratives as we are desperately confronting the loss of planetary crisis. She recommends “a thorough and open rethink which has the courage to question our most basic cultural narratives” (47). Such a strand, in fact boils down to the idea that our scientific paradigm and positivist outlook, our love for the world of nature seem failing as we have grown a disregard which has led mankind to consider nature as mere resource for human consumption. According to this view, many indigenous communities lived in tune with nature and this harmonious cohabitation was the outcome of their negotiation with the world outside which they thought was an expansion of their own socio-cultural spaces.

The word “animism” comes from the Latin word “anima” meaning ‘breath’, ‘spirit’, or ‘life’. The basic premise of this metaphysical concept is founded on the belief in a supernatural universe, superficially, on the conceit of immaterial soul. In simple terms, it holds the idea that nature has her own spirit or soul. Animistic worldview exists in many of the complex societies and hierarchical

religions. The majority of the world religions are not animistic, but a few other religions of the tribal peoples, are animistic. Since the primitive times animism as a religious belief existed among the hunter gatherers across the globe. It cannot be described under a single umbrella term-it has its hierarchies and different ontological explanations and conflicting traditions. In fact, animism is an umbrella term, encompassing a plethora of conflicting traditions and concepts, whereas the concept of vitality is a part of that tradition, much relevant in the context of eco-disaster. The first comprehensive view on animism comes from the Victorian anthropologist, Sir Edward Brunett Tylor's work, *Primitive Culture* (1871). According to Tylor, animism is the most rudimentary form of religion. Before the solidification and shaping of a culture in the prehistoric state, in the stage of evolution of a culture, a tribe needed "a minimum definition of religion" and found it in "the Belief in Spiritual Beings" (Tylor, Vol.1.383). According to E. B. Tylor, animists believe that the natural objects like the rocks, trees and the waterfalls are pervaded by spiritual beings; they consider nature to be animated. The most common trait of all animistic religions is their particularism. In *Natural History of Religion* (1757) David Hume points to the universal propensity of mankind "to conceive all beings like themselves" (Vol.1, Sec-iv, 29). Inanimate bodies are endowed with "invisible powers possessed of sentiment and intelligence" (Hume 42). It is a kind of "mythic personification"(vol.1, 273), says Tylor. Almost echoing the same tune, Sigmund Freud argues that the animists find a kind of "analogy of human souls" in animals, plants, and objects in nature (76). In fact, these writers while deliberating on animism ascribe the natural phenomena with stray anthropomorphism. In *The Golden Bough*, James Frazer refers to animism as "savage dogma" (1900, 171). Rites and rituals relating to animism are described as "mistaken applications" of basic principles of anthropomorphism and an analogy between the human world and the natural world (62). The modernist view, however, championed by the likes of Hume, Tylor, and Frazer as an unsophisticated, primitive, and superstitious belief was called into question in the 20th century. Stewart Guthrie, a modern

proponent, suggests that animistic philosophy requires proper explanation. He goes deep into the matter and tries to understand why people are so prone to invest personhood or agency to non-human agents. Guthrie's stance is that animistic belief is the outcome of an adaptive policy of survival in the process of evolution.

Animism in the parlance of contemporary post-modern social science discussion has gained in momentum, causing a renaissance unseen hitherto. Notable contributors of repute are Philippe Descola, Tim Ingold, Nurit Bird-David, and Graham Harvey. Nurit Bird-David explains animism in terms of "relational epistemology" in which the animate and the inanimate are bound by a social interaction. In this view, the subject-subject relation between the human and the non-human is of fundamental concern, whereas the naturalists take it as the subject-object relation. David's view does not suggest any metaphysical idea that the non-human agents have souls or spirits. Rather, he advocates the idea of socialisation. According to David Bird, any particular tree, for example, is not a person, but by virtue of social interaction or socialisation, the tree becomes a social being. Philippe Descola explains animism as a worldview where the animate and the inanimate share a common "interiority" (soul) but differ only in "exteriority" (physical states). Seen in this light, humans and the natural objects, for example, differ in exteriority; but they share common interior states. This is in stark contrast to the naturalistic worldview that hypothesises the likeness in exteriority and difference in interiority. As the interiority is common to both humans and non-humans alike, it comes to the point that non-humans are said to have social features, such as reverence for kinship rules and ethical conducts. Viveiros de Castro's radical view called "perspectivism", rooted in diverse Amerindian indigenous religions, poses a challenge to the Western nature/culture divide by suggesting a common interiority among all. As perspectivism applies only to a limited number of Amerindian cultures, it cannot be considered an inclusive view of animism. However, Descola and Viveiros de Castro, both converge to the point of ascribing interiority to non-humans as well as to

non-living agents. Tim Ingold's idea of animism does not involve any spirits. He suggests that animism is a lived experience of listening with heightened sensitivity and responsiveness to an environment that is always in a state of flux. Seen in this light, it is a stance of being alive to the world of nature, marked by hypersensitivity and responsiveness, be it in action or perception. Ingold, in fact, emphasises the "lived experience" of animism as "the sense of wonder that comes from riding the crest of the world's continued birth". Irving Hallowell's explication of animism also focuses on the ontology of social relations. In his opinion, "the world is full of persons, only some of whom are human, and that life is always lived in relationship with others" (xi). Such recent ethnographers and anthropologists have tried to explain the modes in which indigenous societies accomplished social relations between the human and the non-human in a process which conspicuously oppose the Western view of social world. Such an attitude can be considered as the New Animism. In this context, it is pertinent to note that animists consider some objects of natural world, for instance, rivers, lakes, trees, mountains, animals and thunderstorms as non-human agents with whom we can extend social rapport. In this connection, it is worth mentioning that many animistic believers consider the objects of natural environment to be non-human relatives or progenitors from whom the community people descended.

Some of the renowned philosophers like Max Horkheimer and Theodor Adorno are of the opinion that modern men are estranged from nature for their naturalistic scientific attitude and this alienation can be cured by resorting to animistic mode of living. Martin Buber's explanation of animism is worth mentioning. He emphasises the fundamental spiritual nature of what he calls the "I-Thou" aspect of experience (a subject-subject relation), which can be contrasted with the "I-It" aspect (a subject-object relation). The pragmatist philosopher William James uses the very same terms while speaking of the religious perception of the universe: "The universe is no longer a mere *It* to us, but a *Thou*" (240). Viewed in this way, the world is made up of a nebulous network of human

and non-human relatives, and maintenance of good relations within it.

Unlike theism, animism down the ages has received negative recognition. The Christian missionaries are unsympathetic to animistic worldview. They consider it as a “primitive superstition”. However, it is a primitive religious credo, inferior but ancestral to their own. To the intellectuals of the 19th century already soaked in the ideologies of Darwin’s theory of evolution, animism is concerned with primitive mind, a stage in the process evolution of culture. Post-modern thinkers take this view to be founded on an erroneous premise.

Amitav Ghosh is an environmental humanist. In a number of his fictional narratives he engages his conscious force to address the issue of climate crisis and very subtly weaves into the texture of his stories the animistic worldview that pleads for socialization between the human and the non-human others. In course of his narratives, in the garb of his stories, he shows how modern men’s failure in recognizing the social non-human others has resulted in a disastrous outcome. In *The Living Mountain: A Fable of Our Times* (2022), Amitav Ghosh’s fictional oeuvre very deftly places the idea of animism by positing the mountain, Mahaparbat as a living force, an animated object of nature. The mountain in the story can “listen” and the tribal people living in the valley are interconnected with the spirit of the mountain. The tenor of their life runs smooth until the Anthropoi (humans) who consider nature as a mere source of consumption appear to act upon her serenity. Ghosh, in order to drive his point as a cautionary anecdote tinges his story in the form of a dream. In the fable, Maansi, in her dream, takes us to a fictitious territory of tribal villages extending across the valley of streams flowing down from the Great Mountain, called the Mahaparbat. The dwellers living there receive sustenance from the natural resources, garnered thriftlessly for ages by the mountain and the streams flowing from the mountain. Despite differences among the villages, all of them converged to a point. They-

revered that mountain: our ancestors had told us that of all the world's mountains ours was the most alive; that it would protect us and look after us-but only on condition that we told stories about it, and sang about it, and danced for it-but always from a distance. For one of the binding laws of the valley, respected by all our warring villages, was that we were never, on any account, to set foot on the slopes of the Great Mountain (Ghosh 7).

The warring villagers never set their foot on the mountain and maintained a social interaction with it. The old women of the tribes, called the adepts, danced and could feel and read the life of the mountain. But the virgin mountain hitherto un-kissed by the footprints of mankind drew the eyes of the strangers called the Anthropoi. They, with their might and mien, defeated the villagers and made them servants who had to work from them, their adepts killed and leaders replaced. They laughed at the beliefs of the villagers of the sacredness of the mountain. They thought: "all ignorant, pagan superstition... All mountains were the same, they could all be climbed if only the climbers were strong" (Ghosh 26). The climbing and digging the mountain started for the consumption of resources. For years the plundering of the natural resources continued and now the villagers, particularly, the favourites of the strangers, also started climbing and finally all the villagers joined them in great numbers. There was now no difference between the strangers and the villagers. In their bid to climb up the mountain, they forgot all limits and one day what happened, a huge iceberg slid down the slope from the bottom of the mountain sweeping several villages in the foothills claiming a huge toll of lives. Still the climbing continued. The Anthropoi were much ahead and the Varvaroi (villagers) following them up. But the climbing is now an addiction, more speedy than before. The late climbers ultimately came to a point where the early climbers halted and thought it not right to climb up more. Suddenly they felt another shock from the mountain as if it is revolting against the advancement of the illegal invaders into her sacrosanct pulpit. Despairing, with their hearts in hands, they came down and found

to believe to have some kind of truth in the words of the Varvaroi and their Adepts, as the savants started saying- “there was some wisdom in your belief after all” (Ghosh 34). Savants of the Anthropoi condescended, “You were right! The mountain is alive! We can feel its heartbeat under our feet. This means we must look after the poor, dear mountain; we must tend to it, we must care for it.” (35). Ghosh’s story therefore places the mountain as a living presence; it is not merely a rock, it is sentient entity and the local villagers have their old stories, songs and dances to honour the mountain with their traditional ecological wisdom. The Anthropoi, having their ingrained belief in extractivism and nature as a source for profit and consumption, commit an epistemic violence by dismissing the indigenous belief in animism as pagan and as a result inviting dangers upon themselves. The denouement is very important where the Anthropoi realises their great mistake and seek the Adept to learn the old ways urging humanity to rediscover animistic principles for survival in the face of climate crisis. Ghosh ultimately advocates a revival of the profound, spiritual connection to the non-human world that indigenous cultures once emphasized.

Ghosh’s novel, *The Hungry Tide* (2004), through the indigenous myth of Bon Bibi, recognizes the existence of non-human agency challenging the anthropocentric Western worldview that leads to the rampant exploitation of nature. The fiction brings side by side the indigenous experience of Fokir, a local fisherman and the scientific approach of a marine biologist, Priya. Fokir and the local people consider the Sundarbans as a living entity, much to the contradiction of Western knowledge of ecology. Priya’s psychological journey from a scientific frame of mind to a relational understanding of environment is worth noticing. Ghosh seems to establish the idea that nature is not a passive force for humanity. Bon Bibi, the forest deity who protects the local people from the tiger god, is a powerful spirit, an agency cherished in animistic philosophy. The other non-human entities like the Irrawaddy dolphins, the mangrove forests, and the powerful tidal currents are depicted as active agents with their own existence and

emotional depths. Nature is a force that doesn't "bend to natural, will" but possesses a wild, untamable quality that humans must learn to respect and cohabit with, rather than control. Through its use of animism and myth, the novel critiques the human/nature dualism prevalent in Western thought. Ghosh argues for reconciliation with nature, suggesting that true ecological awareness must bridge the gap between human societies and the natural world, acknowledging their profound interdependence. In essence, animism in *The Hungry Tide* (2004) is a literary and philosophical tool used to challenge conventional environmentalism and promote an ethics of care and responsibility towards the planet, rooted in ancient and indigenous wisdom. Ghosh's *Gun Island* (2019) exploits the myth of the snake goddess Manasa Devi to embody the environmental and migration crises of our times. The fictional narrative concerns the old legend of the Bonduki Sadagar (Gun Merchant), an affluent tradesman who incurs the displeasure of Manasa Devi, the deity of snakes and fertility as he refused to worship her for his pride and for material gain. She brings natural calamities and sets snakes upon him and drives him away into a long journey across the bay to elude her anger. Ghosh here challenges the secular, rational worldview of the protagonist, Deen Datta, by presenting a world where animals and nature exhibit mysterious and powerful agency. The presence of the poisonous snake, a king cobra, in the Sundarbans, and a yellow-bellied sea snake in Los Angeles, represent "uncanny" events that defy easy scientific explanation and are linked to Manasa Devi's influence and the changing environment. Ultimately, through its animistic elements, *Gun Island* argues for a renewed sense of reverence, humility, and responsibility toward the nonhuman world, suggesting that survival depends on recognizing the interconnectedness of all life.

Nature was created out of a cosmic force; she has her own constitution and the abiding laws. She has her mountains, rivers, trees, the groves and the treasure troves in her bosom. As part of creation, she has both the human and the non-human agents. The seeds of human life have grown in accordance to the same laws of

nature. But human agents alone, in desperate disregard of the laws of nature, defile the sacredness of the space where he lives and breathes. For his aggression for comfort and delusory development he tries to tame nature, despoil her serenity. But who are we to tame it, shape and distort it? Are we as strong as to change her course? We are only a little bit tiny creatures, ever failing to discover her infinite variety and depth. If life in this planet is to be sustained, we must pay meet adoration to the subtle forms of nature. Animism is an indigenous way of paying respect to the natural, inanimate objects. Whether those objects are endowed with souls or spirits may be an issue of investigation to an inquisitive mind, but it is not everything. We would lead ourselves astray if the non-biological agencies are exploited for our ends. In fact, the biological and the non-biological phenomena are interdependent. Without the non-biological phenomena nothing can exist. So, it is not important to hair-split whether animistic philosophy has some factual ground or not, whether the natural objects have souls or not. If our sole motif is to save the serenity of the natural world, any philosophy satisfying our objective might be welcome and in that case the gain is always greater, and the price we have to pay against the backdrop of climate crisis is less. Otherwise, the price to be paid for our irreverence is high. Different modes endeavours are being tried to do proper justice with environment. So, there is no harm, if we if we have our reverence to different dimension of animism. The gain in that case is greater, with no loss as a consequence. Let our belief in animism enjoy its heyday and the human and no-human agents live long being interconnected ushering a sustainable nature that remains protected. If the non-human agents are protected, the living beings are also protected.

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